

TRANSITION MINIMIZATION WITH PHASE-SHIFT ENCODING

(pre-review manuscript)

Michael L. Rieger

Consultant, Skamania, WA, USA

mike@MLRieger.com

Abstract

An encoding method for serial digital communication is described where the electrical waveform has 33% fewer transitions between high and low voltage states compared to NRZ for the same data rate, and where the minimum pulse width is limited to $1\frac{1}{2}$ clock cycles. This method, phase-shift encoding (PSE), is enabled by modulating the phase of voltage transition edges between 0 and 180 degrees with respect to the clock. That phase information is leveraged to reduce the waveform transition rate.

keywords: VLSI power density, transition minimization.

Introduction

As transistor density continues to rise in advancing VLSI technology, innovation in architecture and circuit design increasingly is required to manage chip power density [1]. In CMOS integrated circuits, each voltage transition dissipates energy, $E_t = \frac{1}{2}CV^2 J$, and dynamic power is the number of voltage state transitions per second times E_t . Transferring data consumes substantial power in modern VLSI circuits [2], and various coding methods have been deployed to minimize signal transitions for power minimization [3].

PSE Encode/Decode Concept

Fig. 1 Basic concept: binary sequence (left side) and encoded signal (right). Tick marks correspond to clock cycles, period T.

The concept is to copy the input binary stream to the encoded output, bit by bit, except for intercepting any isolated, single-clock-wide period (T sec.) pulse and replacing it, and the subsequent bit, with a phase-shifted, $1\frac{1}{2} T$ wide pulse, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The decoder copies the encoded stream except for when a phase-shifted edge is detected, whereupon the original binary pattern (2 consecutive bits) is reconstructed.

A. Encoder Logic

An encoding circuit is shown in Fig. 3. The output waveform is constructed from logic states S1 and S2, corresponding to the first and second halves of a symmetric

clock cycle. A typical binary sequence and its corresponding encoded waveform is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 3 Encoding circuit. Truth table for logic is provided in Fig 4.

The logic block truth table is shown in Fig. 4 (left), with the encoder circuit state-transition diagram (right) mapping its 6 reachable memory states labeled A-F. The probabilities of all state-change arcs are $1/2$ given a random, symmetric input stream of binary values

	Memory	In	Out				
States	LP	LS2	LU	U	P	S2	S1
A	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
B	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
	0	0	1	1	0	1	1
C	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
D	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
	1	0	0	1	X	X	X
E	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
F	1	1	0	0	0	1	1
	1	1	0	1	0	1	1
	1	1	1	0	X	X	X
	1	1	1	1	X	X	X

Fig. 4 Truth table (left) for encoder logic block in Fig. 3. Markov discrete process (right), where all state-change probabilities are $1/2$, and where double-line arcs denote those state changes producing a transition on the output waveform.

The steady-state probability for each encoder state is obtained by solving the state-transition matrix (1) for its Markov stationary distribution (Table 1, column 2). Only encoder state changes AB, EB, FC, and DC each produce one transition in the encoded waveform, and those transition probabilities per clock are in Table 1, column 5. The average rate of transitions per clock is $1/3$, the sum of those state change

Fig 2 Example binary serial input (upper) and its PSE encoded waveform (lower, latency removed).

probabilities in col. 5. This is a 33% reduction in average signal transition rate compared to NRZ, which has an average transition rate of 1/2.

$$\begin{matrix} A \\ B \\ C \\ D \\ E \\ F \end{matrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{2} & \frac{1}{2} & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Table 1 Encoder Markov stationary distribution and PSE waveform transition probabilities per clock for a random binary input stream.

State	Markov SD	Trans. to	P(trans)	Ptrans)
A	1/4	B	1/4 · 1/2	1/8
B	1/6			
C	1/6			
D	1/4	C	1/4 · 1/2	1/8
E	1/12	B	1/12 · 1/2	1/24
F	1/12	C	1/12 · 1/2	1/24
Total	1			1/3

B. Decoder

Fig. 5 Decoder circuit.

The decoder, Fig. 5, copies the input to the output except for when a phase shifted edge is encountered. Phase detection at the decoder is accomplished by sampling the encoded signal at \rightarrow clock and comparing that sample to the signal with an XOR gate before next rising clock. The risetime of the (conditioned) encoded waveform must be shorter than $\frac{1}{2}$ clock period T to detect the phase shift. When a phase shift is detected, the decoder produces two consecutive bits (high-low or low-high) on the next two clocks.

Net latency from logic processes through encoding and decoding is $3T$: T from encoding plus $2T$ from decoding.

C. Frequency and Bandwidth

The power spectrum for a PSE encoded waveform is significantly narrower than that for an NRZ waveform. Fig. 6 shows FFT results comparing $|F|^2$ for unipolar NRZ and PSE (for very-long series of random input bits).

Compared to NRZ, where the minimum pulse width is T , the shortest pulse in a PSE encoded waveform is $\frac{1}{2} T$. Furthermore, because any $\frac{1}{2} T$ pulse must have neighbor states no shorter than $2T$, the minimum span of any two consecutive voltage states – high-low, or low-high – is $3\frac{1}{2} T$. In effect, the encoding folds high frequency information from the input into lower frequency components in the PSE waveform.

Fig 6 Relative power spectra of NRZ and PSE waveforms.

D. Noise

Phase detection reliability depends on lower edge-arrival-time uncertainty (jitter) compared to NRZ. Amplitude tolerance remains the same. A phase-detection error usually corrupts two consecutive bits in decoded output (though 1-bit errors can occur as well). This behavior needs to be accounted in designing error detection and correction schemes.

E. PAM3 Variant

Fig. 7 Example PAM3 waveform (lower trace, latency removed).

A variation of the PSE encoding pattern, Fig 7, gives a type of 3-level pulse amplitude modulation (PAM3), where an intermediate voltage serves in place of a phase-shifted edge. With the same bit rate as NRZ, and conservatively assuming the dynamic energy for two consecutive stepped transitions is the same as for full swing transitions, the dynamic power saving is 33% -- same as that for PSE. The analog circuitry needed for encoding and decoding is more complex than for PSE, and handling an intermediate voltage signal makes this scheme incompatible with conventional, binary logic buffers and repeaters.

Conclusion

PSE and its PAM3-like variant are aimed at reducing power while maintaining a data-transfer bitrate equal to that of NRZ. Lengthened minimum pulse widths for PSE suggest that data bit rates can be increased beyond NRZ limits within the same channel bandwidths. Further study is needed to determine minimum channel bandwidths with respect to noise and error rates.

References

- [1] M.L. Rieger, "Retrospective on VLSI value scaling and lithography," *J. of Micro/nanolithography, MEMs, and MOEMS*, 18(4), 040902 (2019), DOI: 10.1117/1.JMM.18.4.040902
- [2] V. Raghunathan, M.B. Srivastava, R.K. Gupta, "A survey of techniques for energy efficient on-chip communication," *Proc. ACM/IEEE DAC*, pp. 900-905, 2003, DOI: 10.1145/775832.776059
- [3] M.R. Stan, W.P. Bursleson, "Low-Power Encodings for Global Communication in CMOS VLSI," *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems*, Vol. 5, No. 4, (1997), DOI: 10.1109/92.645071
- [4] M.L. Rieger, "Phase-Shifting Encoding for Signal Transition Minimization," US Patent 11,088,705.